

IDENTIFIES THE PROBLEMS AND DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS IN TRANSLATION
IDIOMS

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Abstract: *This research reports the problems and solutions of translation particularly translation of idioms from English into Uzbek. Those problems are taken from three main factors that consist of objective factor, generic factor, and affective factor.*

Key words: *idiom, speech unit, literary translation, semantic translation, structure of an idiom.*

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Literary translation has its own linguistic specificity, which is associated not only with an adequate transfer of the meaning of a word from one language to another, but also with an equivalent display of the artistic power and expressiveness of one language through another, as to create the necessary artistic formalization in translation is possible only through language material.

When translating, the language is the main tool of the translator, which imposes a huge responsibility on him before the original being translated. This circumstance requires deep knowledge not only in the field of linguistics, but also in matters of culture, everyday life, customs, traditions of various peoples, which are reunited with each other in literary translation. Just like a writer, a translator needs to have observation, deep life experience, emotional openness, sensuality, logic, accurate perception of the world around him and a conscious attitude to his experiences. Since only with its full armament with the necessary knowledge of all the features of both cultures and the mental characteristics of peoples, it becomes possible to fully display the alien cultural environment while preserving the unique national flavor of the translated material.

Otherwise, when reflecting the cultural environment of the original, the translator may instead of the reflections of foreign culture, present the reader with elements of his national culture. One of the main criteria of literary translation is the ability to convey the national flavor of the original without equating it with its own national culture.

In this regard, the question of translating English idioms into another language, which have as characteristic only idioms have a unique content, and a special indestructible phraseological uniform structure. It is a very difficult task to preserve the lexical, semantic and

linguistic features of idioms. An idiom is an unmoded word combination that operates more on the principles of semantic unity than an internal ordered structure. Thus, in linguistic use, such combinations are not created on the basis of certain models, but are used in their ready-made, already accepted and existing form. Therefore, an idiom is a whole semantic structure. Semantics in this structure plays a dominant role. But the semantics does not depend on the meaning of the words that form the idiom. Words, uniting in the structure of an idiom, in most cases lose their original meaning. Also, it is very difficult to translate an idiom into another language without knowing the real meaning of this phraseological unit (mare's nest - nonsense; spill the beans - reveal a secret). Idioms are a special linguistic phenomenon and demonstrate linguistic, semantic, artistic richness language, its wide possibilities, diversity and uniqueness. Knowledge of idioms makes learning extremely easy both journalistic and fiction.

It is very important to teach idioms for students of faculties of foreign languages, the ability to understand and correctly translate idioms of the target language.

It is known, the structure of the English language differs from the structure of the Uzbek language from the genetic point of view, they belong to different language families. As a consequence, the grammatical structure of these languages is also different from each other. For example, in Uzbek language, there are many affixes in the language, a sentence begins with a noun and ends with a verb, there are not prepositions, articles, gender categories. On the contrary, in English language, there are articles, prepositions, and affixes. Therefore, when studying and translating words, phrases, sentences, and especially idioms arise certain difficulties. In addition, the mutual difference in the form and meaning of English and Uzbek idioms creates difficulties in their translation. Of course, if the student thinks logically, then he can find some similarity, associative options, but when students hear English idioms for the first time, then they only take their form, completely without delving into out meaning or content. For example, "hot under the collar" is literally translated into Uzbek "ёқа остидаги иссиқлик" (hot under the collar), whereas the equivalent of this idioms in Uzbek is "тепа сочи тикка бўлди" (hair stand on end). As you can see from the example, the difference in form and meaning is the difficulty in assimilation of idioms. U. Hoshimov and I. Yokubov in the book "Methods of Teaching English" emphasized that the difficulties, encountering during the assimilation of words arise, based on its form, semantics and applications. D. Nurmuratova classifies the difficulties in the study of idioms of the English language into four groups:

1. The first group includes international combinations that do not cause difficulties in their study. They are familiar to students or meet in their native language. For example: Achilles hell; flat broke; right now; as for house - wife.

2. A characteristic feature of the second group is their belonging in their form and semantics only to that or another language. For example: to leave school (literally: leave school) – мактабни битирмоқ (finish school; beat the band (literally: beat the band) – жон-жаҳди билан ишга киришмоқ (get to work vigorously). If proceed form from form of turns, it can be said that idioms in English begin with a verb, and in Uzbek language they begin with a noun and are read by a verb. Big fish (literally: big fish) – обрўли шахс (authoritative, person

of a great rank). From a semantic point of view, this combination occurs only in English (compare with colloquial Russian: big shot). The combination “Big fish” is not found in the Uzbek language. It is used in English in relation to high officials.

3. Idioms of the third group are found in both languages. From some side they are similar, but on the other hand they differ from each other. For example: “Cry over spilled milk” means “Сўнги пушаймон ўзинга душман” in Uzbek language. “Give a ring” means “Сим қоқмоқ”, they differ mainly in shape, but are similar in meaning. But they differ in shape, so students admit errors in their application.

4. The basis of the fourth group is polysemantics, when a idiom has many meanings. For example: “All thumbs” can mean in Uzbek “Ўнғайсизлик” (inconvenience, awkward position), омадсиз кун (bad day), чап ёндан турмоқ (get up with your left foot). “Gift of gab” can mean “аравани қуруқ олиб қочиш ” (to run away with an empty cart). These idioms cannot be defined by any one exact combination, so they give rise to difficulties in assimilation.

The students do not make mistakes in the assimilation and translation of idioms of the English language, it is necessary to explain to them their meaning and cases of application, explain that the difference in form and meaning is the influence of the fact that these languages belong to different language families. Under the influence of this main factor idioms layers in different situations and contexts that can express different concepts and images.

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